

Participant 6

SUMMARY KEYWORDS

coding, project, client, team, developer, team member, moment, mistakes, quality, issue, admin panel, totally, agree, talk, work, problem, company, requirement, lead, person

SPEAKERS

Researcher

Participant 6

Researcher 00:12

Good morning. Can you hear me? Good morning.

Participant 6 00:31

Hi, good morning. Can you hear me?

Researcher 00:33

Yeah, I can hear you. How are you this morning? It's not the morning. What time is it?

Participant 6 00:45

It's the evening?

Researcher 00:46

Yes. We almost eight hour apart, right?

Participant 6 00:50

I think it's four and a half hours.

Researcher 00:53

Oh, ok. Yeah. I thought it's only 12 hour or eight hours. Okay, not been. Thanks a lot for the interview. I appreciate and I'm looking forward to the discussion. Okay, I do have a lot to go through. And I'd like to start by doing some introduction. Would you like to introduce yourself and mainly your education and experience?

Participant 6 01:23

My name is Participant 6. And I'm 30 years old . Eight years in information technology. And I've been in IT field for something like eight years, currently working as a senior software engineer. Yeah, I think that's it.

Researcher 01:45

Yeah. Okay. That's enough. So, currently, you working on an agile environment, you using agile in your team, right?

Participant 6 01:58

Yeah, we are using agile, but at the moment, we are working on it. And so this project was previously done by another team. Even this is even we are working on agile. Sometimes we have to go apart from Agile. It is mainly a Scrum implementation.

Researcher 02:21

Yeah. Yes. So when you say you go apart from Agile, what do you mean?

Participant 6 02:29

No. Usually we would take one part and we will talk as a group for I mean, we would take one story, then we will all together poke about this. But at the moment, in our current with our current deadlines is bit hard to talk with everyone. So what we do is, especially our PM, he thinks, Okay, this part is the he will he think that this part can be done by someone else this can be done by summary. So he just say are the tasks with us. So there is no time for us to talk as a group at the moment.

Researcher 03:25

Because of the COVID, or that's always been the case.

Participant 6 03:29

And now the project was initially done by another team. But so but we have to deliver the things to the client as he agreed. So that's the reason actually.

Researcher 03:43

Okay, I understand. Thank you. How big is the team, the current team? You work?

Participant 6 03:50

Currently are eight team members

Researcher 03:59

Are cross functional or only developers?

Participant 6 04:04

Seven of them for front end developers, and me and our lead. We both coding at the backend. Back to back.

Researcher 04:19

Okay. How long have you been working together? Is it a newly formed team or you've been working together for a while? And are you self-managed? What type of projects you develop?

Participant 6 04:29

This is a newly formed team. I'll be joined with them. I think it's been five months. Partly self-managed. At the moment the project manager takes a lot of decisions. We get different projects from UK clients. Mostly custom software or enhancements.

Researcher 04:36

Okay. Yeah. Okay. All right. Thanks for sending those answer on the email. I really appreciate we're gonna work on them one by one. And we're going to discuss some examples. But before we do that, we will be talking about software quality on those examples. So before we due that I'd like to clarify what do we mean by software quality. So just to make sure we are on the same page, so we use a definition from ISO standards, and I'll read it to you and we can discuss it briefly and we can move on with the questions. So, the ISO definition states quality is the degree to which the system satisfy the stated and implied needs of the various stakeholders, and does provide value. It also covers a lot of non functional characteristics, mainly performance, compatibility, usability, you know, all these non functional requirements like reliability, security, maintainability, and portability. So, what do you think about this definition? Do you agree with it? And would you like to comment on it?

Participant 6 06:06

Yeah, I agree with it. But okay, if we go for the quality of the software, if I am the client, I may think, okay, I need nice background and nice UI, I need all the buttons should be work, I need the, basically, if I'm the client, I need things, I need to see things, colourful, most of the plants, that's how they think. The the, the way, quality been described is correct. But if we think as a developer, they may have a different definition. If we think as scrum master or PM, they will agree what I said, client need to say something amazing, and he needs to see it in colourful way. But if we go for the developer, as a developer quality mean, not only the functionality, mainly functionality, but for example, the project currently I am working. It has been caught by, I think three or four developers. Same functionality happens in different locations, but different coding. So as a developer, I think, quality mean, from my side, this thing, if you think about that functionality, it should be in only one location. So that mean, even another year, someone would join the company, they should be able to find the location, and they know, okay, this method is possible for all other functionalities. So from clients perspective, it's been different. But from development perspective, it's totally different with the science idea.

Researcher 08:20

Yeah. So you were you, you, in addition to the external aspect of the software, you also focus on the internal aspect of the software, for example, you're talking about a design that is sustainable, maintainable. So we could scale it in the future. So a future developer can work with your solution, right? That's what you meant.

Participant 6 08:43

Yeah. If I develop something, if it's urgent, I will do something and it could work, but when project becomes bigger, everyone should think what could happen in the future? Basically, what I mean it should be simple and it should be scalable and maintainable.

Researcher 09:05

I agree with you. Yes. So, this definition is more and user focus. Yeah, I agree with you. Yeah. So, to achieve quality, you must have some quality assurance practices and processes. What do you use for quality assurance?

Participant 6 09:28

You mean for coding structures?

Researcher 09:30

So yes, coding standard code review testing, unit testing, what do you do?

Participant 6 09:37

Basically, what we do is we always follow PSR standards. I think not only as most of the companies do, but in my experience what I have seen is when if I do work for a new company, they will say okay, we are following these structures, you need to follow it. The only the issue As they mentioned it only at the interview only in the first days, but after a couple of days, or they don't remember about the standard. So, yeah, we use PSR standards. And also, as a team, we always follow a party. They're a good company, I think, based on Belgium, so we always follow the accordance. And for the testing, yeah, I know, for the testing unit test automation test, the standard methods, but for last five years, I haven't seen any company who's using those testing, all the companies, they prefer manual testing. So in books or in tutorial, per se, you need to use unit testing or feature testing. But I haven't seen anything like much automation in my last four years. So we do manual testing and for the standards, PSR standards. And yeah, things like that. Those are things for you to follow.

Researcher 11:17

Okay. So do you have any software engineering? Best practices? You mentioned PCR standards? What other practices do you use?

Participant 6 11:36

Surely DSRM party? I think that's all we use at the moment.

Researcher 11:49

So do you have continuous integration? Do you have? Yeah, yeah. Okay. We will move to the next part of the interview. So basically, from the answer you provided, I think that you work relatively in a safe work environment. So what do I mean by that? I'll explain to you and we can discuss, what do I mean by a safe work environment is an environment that provides a sense of security from repercussions. So you and your team member feel that it's okay to admit mistakes, you feel that it's okay to propose initiatives and discuss problems. So there is a sense of confidence in the team that the team would not embarrass or reject or punish someone for speaking. So this confidence stems from the material respect and trust amongst the team members. So do you agree with me, that's the team that you work on in at the moment is a relatively safe work environment? Like I described it? Yeah. So to what extent do you agree Do you strongly agree, do you agree, neutral disagree or strongly disagree?

Participant 6 13:14

I haven't. I think, yeah, I strongly agree with that. So I think it's before two weeks, I got addition that I should resign from my current job. The reason is, in 2021, I did three projects for UK company, and for sorry, in 2020, but in 2021, I am still on one project. So I thought, okay, they are not going to move forward, something is new, so I thought I should resign them. I went to a pm and I talked to him, I said, Hey, I need to resign. And I said, I will not resign today, but I will resign now for three months. He actually, he managed that problem properly, as much as the issue important. So I said, we are just having one project. I don't see. I actually I said I don't see any future for me here. So then he said a lot of things. He said, after this, we have this type of plans, we have this type of projects, and he has for me, please reconsider about your decision. So with that, I felt happy, because he showed me that he needed me to be in the team all the time. So as a PM, I think as a PM, he managed that problem properly. He said okay, think again. We will talk about this tomorrow. So after that discussion, I feel more confident that I am in a safe environment. So yeah, actually, I totally agree with you.

Researcher 15:10

Okay, so what made you decide is this safe because he acknowledges your skills, and he appreciate your work?

Participant 6 15:22

Actually, I have job security. The reason is here, to be honest, I can be with this project for next couple of years. And I know I am safe economically and financial everything. But what I want is, I wanted something new. And but the problem is he didn't mention those future plans, at any date. So that's the reason I thought I need to resign. But when I see, okay, we have a plan like this, there will be exciting new projects, then yeah, there is no reason for me to leave. Because at the moment, getting a good salary, and especially my work environment, I have good salary where I work. They need all the developers to be online. I mean, they need to be in a call all the time. But personally, it is hard for me, usually with our current PM, just take a call at 9am. And that's all for today. He know who we are. And he know, no matter whatever the time is, if it's urgent, oh, we will do it. So yeah, that's, I have that freedom. So I really appreciate in my job, I am a person who really appreciate my freedom.

Researcher 16:46

Fantastic. Happy to hear that. So what do you think has made this environment safe? Do you think because you have a good project manager or you have a good team? So?

Participant 6 17:01

Yeah, so when I joined this company, I think on last year, September. At that moment, there were six members, all of us who are new to the project. And when it comes for December, I was the only one who was there a step further five members resigned. So the reason was, I just had a course with two members. And they said, This is too much pressure. And I can't work in an environment like this. So I don't know, I didn't feel something like that. Because before this project, I was one of my friends started at the company. And at that moment, there were only me, he and another one friend. So what year, there were more than three to 40 developers. So at that time, we had a lot of pressures. Somewhere, especially our client was based in the UK, there is a time gap between us and them. Sometimes I was joining for the meeting very late. So I am a person who don't like to work with some sort of pressure like

that. So when I get the location like this, I don't see any pressure here. So I am the only one who didn't resign the rest of the team members resigned, and left, we are having another couple of new developers. So I think at the moment we have a team, we know what we should achieve. So yeah. So management has changed, we have a lot of freedom, the listen and they adjust the client expectations all the time and they try to protect us from the client pressuring us. We feel much much less pressure.

Researcher 18:58

Okay, fantastic. Yeah, I'm happy that you, you, you happy with your new job. So let's move on to the questions. Sorry, I've sent in the email. So the first statement says, if you make mistakes on your team, it's often held against you. And your answer is it is called done. Definitely yes. But with my experience, this is totally based on the scrum master or project manager. The way they respond will always affect other team, our team members and with the time team member also try to do that. So can you elaborate a little bit on this answer?

Participant 6 19:44

Yeah, definitely that's totally true. But as I said, Yes, it will depend on the PM. Sometimes there will be a developer who is really, really talented. But as humans, he may be, he may do some mistakes, or he may do something that may be not really related to project. The reason what I see is he may not understand the exact requirements, may be PM know everything. But the developer doesn't know all the scenarios. So, yes, if there is coding issue, definitely, it will come back to us. So, with my experience in my previous project, we had a UK project, and it was actually, it was started by me and someone else, but a couple of weeks, I have to move into another project. And when I rejoined for that project, I think it's one or two months, so entire structure has been changed. So, the first day, it's something related to video on the first day, they said, people, we need this, please make it quickly. And I did it. But there were some issues with the video streaming. So the problem is, I just came for the project after two months, and it has been totally changed. So at that moment, the problem was I don't know the exact requirement, but it's working, but they will see issue. So actually, it is it is related to code. But with the requirement, I know it is working, but techniques say this is not working. Why didn't you do something like this? And I didn't say anything. I said, Okay, I'll fix it. But the guy who was working with me, tech lead, leave the call. He said, Yeah, people, I know what the issue is. So don't think about it. We'll fix it. So I think personally, I think he should think, Oh, this guy just joined back to the project. He really don't know what this is at the moment. So I think we can manage that problem bit in a different manner. Just in wildly do you do? Why do you get something like this?

Researcher 22:46

So he blamed you even though you were new to the project? How did how did it make you feel?

Participant 6 22:55

It really is very bad. So he didn't blame but the voice I know how he should talked. It wasn't normal this time and with his voice, we can feel it or is talking with anger.

Researcher 23:14

Yeah. So yeah, that's indirect blame anywhere. The voice can say a lot of things. Yeah. You can read a lot of things on the voice. So did it demotivate you How did you feel as a team member?

Participant 6 23:30

As a team member at that moment, is it the motivation because I just joined with the project and I was in a bit large for the for that two months. But since I had a good team member, he knew that situation. He knew this is not your fault. So he had a discussion with me. And actually, after that, we had me Amen. Other girl as a team. Even after my resignation, they are still calling me. I mean, we had a good understanding that is what really, really important when working as a team. Okay, never. Now, things have changed. Management made is clear no blaming.

Researcher 24:18

Yeah, that was a negative example. Do you know when your team you said it is much safer? Do you have a positive example where you or a team member admitted a mistake? Related to code or related to defect or?

Participant 6 24:39

Yeah, so. Yeah. So after a couple of months, the project was actually successful. client was really happy. So then we know okay, the project will be always with us. So after that, we had something called So far, and it's not really a mistake, but none of us knew there was a noise issue. Actually, it was not generated by us, it was generated by an external API, but because of some of our coding changes entirely go down. So however, at that moment, our PM didn't blame us. So at that moment, which I am the one who changed that. So yeah, at that moment, he totally made that decision totally in a different I mean, appropriate us in a friendly manner? And he said, okay, there is nothing we can do. Let's fix this one. And I think, at first point he was bit scare, is caring about, we may have lost this project. But after a couple of months, he No, okay, the project will be with us. So, yeah, at that moment, he just managed it in a perfect manner.

Researcher 26:22

Okay, so what did you learn from this attitude, which the problem or the mistake was handled in a constructive manner? So what did you learn what happened after that?

Participant 6 26:38

After then everything is fine. So we saw that he has been changed. So that's what we saw from him with his with our team talks, if he knew that, as I said before, at the beginning, he was a bit worried that project may go for someone else. But as soon as you know, okay, this is going to be with us, is totally okay. And actually, sometime he is working with us, not as the tech lead, though, PM, is sometimes to call us as friends. So it totally changed it, but it took a lot of time to see changes. But personally, I think that time is too much, because at that time, a man can leave the team. Now, after the friendly reaction to my mistake which has put production down, I felt confident it's ok to make mistakes.

Researcher 27:38

Yeah, that's true. So this, this positive attitude of your manager to work making mistakes? Did it change your behaviour or the team behaviour to work the quality of your work? Yeah, yeah. Yeah.

Participant 6 27:56

Yeah. So instead of blaming, when he talks like that, or not, especially, we felt some sort of feeling that we are not guilty. Okay. I have done this. And this has been happen, this has changed a lot of things in the project. So when you have that feeling, we don't think about the time, we don't think about the hours we are working, we always try to deliver our best thing to him. So as a leader, not only in this field, as a leader, he, he should earn our respect, he should earn the trust from us. If he is capable to earn it, everyone, everyone will do something more than he expect. So actually, the project was one year, but deliver it within eight months, we completed the entire project.

Researcher 29:03

Okay, fantastic. So the efficiency of the team got better. Does it mean also the quality of your work gets better? Yes. Yes. How did you notice the quality gets better?

Participant 6 29:16

So, for example, from the development perspective, we had we had a testing called penetration testing. It was done by some security guru. And he said it was the first application he was not able to break in. So it was a, it was a big achievement for all of us. So even for the tech lead. So from that, that's from a development perspective, if we go for the client perspective, Actually, we did things more than they asked us to do. So initially, when we proposed just the calendar and a video for but with our ideas at the moment, their initial requirements for the project is totally different. The reason is, as a team, we knew what he wanted, and we just developed it. And then by time, we knew what is the core of this project is, and then we saw this project can be expanded in many better ways. And we had close relationship with the product owner. And he said, Okay, guys, if you think this can be done, it's up to you just do it and show me. So that's how we proposed and developed a better solution, not only the design but the usability and better features.

Researcher 30:50

So defect wise from the customer perspective. Did you notice any improvement and defect?

Participant 6 31:01

You mean, where they are in bugs? Yeah. Yeah, definitely there are significant improvement. Not only less bugs but how we deal with bugs. Usually, if it is really, really urgent, client directly talk to us, he will put a message in Slack and we will fix those things. So also, there were times like, bugs that even client don't know it's about. So we took initiatives to correct them without they tell us. So we had things like that. As I said before, when we get the trust of clients, he know, yeah, there can be best, but these guys are capable. So yeah, personally, I think there would be no bug free application. But our confidence to deal with them is better and we don't feel guilty and we fix them fast and make the code even better when we fix.

Researcher 32:21

Okay, fantastic. Thank you. We will move to the next item, which is says members of your team can bring these up problems and tough issues. You said yes. Why not? All are humans, sometimes members don't ask question. And they build develop something which is totally different from the client requirements. When the scrum master project manager asked about the reasons they will say I was

thinking like this. So yes, anyone in the team can bring problems, even the scrum, masters and manage. So do you have an example where someone came forward with a problem related to quality and how we dealt with it as a team?

33:11

Yeah. So for example, this project. The entire project UIs was based on a couple of colours, red, black and white. So client always has this should be in. So those were their theme colours. But unfortunately, by one of our own mistake, we have put green colour there. So actually, we none of us noticed, developers, the testers, even the person who gather requirements, none of us saw that. So when it went for the client, he just say, Hey, what is this? And he said, at that moment, actually, he said, I can't work with two guys, I may be trying to find a new team. The only reason was just a small colour chain. So actually, it's a mistake, as I said, None of us. So what was the issue there? It's a mistake. So that time was a very tough time. Because when clients say, I maybe need to move this project to another new team. We did a lot of good things. And they did a lot of things he expected but because of a small chain, he was able to change all of our minds. So yeah, or like humans, there can be mistakes, actually, there can be issues.

Researcher 34:53

So what happened? You didn't explain to me what happens. You Yeah, the problem was identified. By and the client was not happy. So what happened?

Participant 6 35:04

So immediately, we said, we dropped the call, we said, we'll get back to you. Perfect. Actually, it was just a colour issue. It didn't take much time. So we had to fix it again. And then we tried to have a call with the client again, he said, No, I can't at the moment. And at that, he said, let's meet on tomorrow. So we complete those issues. And we had the demo after they after that call. So he was happy. But as I see, sometimes even we complete the project. Sometimes he always tried to mention that issue. Even though now project is a big programme, that application, sometimes he tried to mention that issue. So yeah, we were able to fix it. But that was something like a black map for entire team. But our manager talked to him. He made it clear that his attitude was not acceptable. We did our best and fixed the problem. We felt nice and very safe that our manager stood up for us.

Researcher 36:09

So as a team, what did you learn from this experience? What did you learn as a team?

Participant 6 36:16

So as a team, as I said, as a client, they see things, beautiful, they, that's what they see. So what we learned was, before we go for the client, we should have someone for the very close to client, who know about the project as much as planned, but he should be friendly with us more than plan. So we, later on, we talked with the client, and he gave us a person who actually didn't know about the project, just like blind but with time, he knew everything. And he is really friendly. Does he say, oh, please make this purchase. Please make this Paddy. Like that. So when we have someone like that we know, even their issue. He even he don't want to show those issues require. So instead of directly going for the client, there should be some middleman.

Researcher 37:31

So he should. So he shield you from the frustration of the client, and he made things work better, right? Yeah. So that so did this experience make you avoid the same mistakes in the future?

Participant 6 37:49

Yes. Because this one before we show any demo for the client. So many times, our team members as a team we discussed, actually, we went through each word in the requirement even though if they send us an email, email template, if they said this dot should be here. We were checking every word. Very careful. So ask a team it's a very good point that we learn about clients. We take time to understand the requirements, we don't make assumptions if we don't understand.

Researcher 38:29

Okay, fantastic. Let's move to the next one which says people on your team sometimes reject for being different. What we mean by reject is someone has different ideas, someone who has different way of working we didn't mean the person for any other human basis, either religion or ethnicity or etc. So your answer says yes, but as I see this happening because of the person personality Yes, the reason is even though you are perfect developer if you don't have good personality, good communication skills. Other team member always try to reject or ignore them because the people like always want to with the development. But when it comes to social, it's hard when work with other Yeah, I agree with you. Can you elaborate and if you have a good example would be nice.

Participant 6 39:38

Yeah, best example would be me. I'm not. I'm a bit silent guy. So in my team, I think I did something bigger than I talk. So but the other member

Participant 6 40:02

They may not do things like me, but they are capable to talk even about my tasks, they are capable to talk about them. So, actually, that is the reason for my previous job resignation. So I do a lot. And all most of the time someone is talking about it. Oh, we have that. At that moment they talk as Vi. But no one wants to say, This guy did. So actually, it's not, actually it's my fault, because I know. I know, I'm not talking too much. And be silent. So yeah, if I think communication is really, really important. Because even you do something or even your door, you should be, we should be able to say, Yes, I did this, I did this in this way. And I use these technologies, these coding structures, if I wasn't able to do something, I should be able to Sorry, I wasn't able to do this. This is the reason I didn't really knew about these things. So communication, if I don't communicate well, no matter how many years of experience I do have, it's it's really bad for my carrier in a team, because there can be one person, a talkative guy, who always want to be with others, but he may not do a lot of tasks. So yes, there is the personality, I mean, good communication skills are really important. Otherwise, developer can be rejected. Team is not doing it in as a team, they may not want to do it. But sometimes, we've failed that oh, these isl ignoring me, what they show with me, I'm doing coding? Well, I am doing my part. The reason is my communication problem. That's why I said the best example would be me.

Researcher 42:37

So is it communication or openness? What do you think, is because you don't communicate much or you are not open about the way you work? Or both?

Participant 6 42:51

I think both because personally, I think we don't need to share our personal life in not only in this field, because I know there are people who use those things

Participant 6 43:07

when they need to do something. But most of the leaders who I have, they would like to know our personal life. So

Participant 6 43:22

But I think we shouldn't shy. So actually, this was the reason for my resignation. So I think there should be a limit as a lead as a developer, there should be a limit for everything. So yeah, I think I have both issues you mentioned.

Researcher 43:44

So do you have an example where your lack of or you don't communicate enough, you are not open enough, has affected the quality of your work or has affected the quality of your work?

Participant 6 44:06

When it comes for the coding, actually, that didn't ask for my coding, because I always wanted to do my best. But in my previous job, I was not only for a developer before this development, before this development industry, I was working as a planning executive for six years. So more than 50 people were working under my supervision. So I think when I was rejected like that, not from the coding, but from some sides. There were some issues because personally I know personally, my lead stays neutral, you are doing things good. But I think you really talented for management. So he always try to mention them. Each time when we go for a call, actually, I was managing two major projects there. Monday and Friday, I am always in client meetings, and other traders, I am directly coding for those two projects. But for the time that he said those, you are good for the management or for the coding. So, actually, so after that I was resigned from that company. Ignoring like, that won't effect my code. But it because of that ignoring the last person, I think they lost a person like me.

Researcher 45:51

Yeah, that's unfortunate. Yeah. But now in this team, which is much safer. Do you feel like you can be more open?

Participant 6 46:02

Yeah, but as, as my role I never open my personal life.

Researcher 46:10

No, no, it doesn't have to be I don't mean openness about your personal life, openness about the way you work openness about? Yes. So I didn't mean openness about your personal life. I'm like that I don't, I don't share my personal life at work. But what we mean by openness is sharing your idea is coming forward when there is problem. So in this team, you become more open because it's safe.

Participant 6 46:38

Yeah, actually, I knew that communication is one of my weaknesses. I think I was able to fix it within a couple of months. At the beginning, when I joined the project, I was not talking much. But now. Even my lead said, Participant 6, you have all the time for questions. Just send me a message. We don't need to talk. He didn't just said it. He just laughed it finally saying that. So I think my communication issue is now fixed.

Researcher 47:17

Okay, fantastic. Do you think it's fixed because of this of this safety that this team has provided to you? Did it help?

Participant 6 47:27

Yeah, I think not only for his development, even in my life, I'm not much talkative. But I think it took me 27 years to understand. I need to improve my communication, even in my personal life. I think I have improved my communication issue. But, yes when you have safety it helps to open up because I always feel nobody would judge me.

Researcher 47:49

Okay, fantastic. Let's move to the next item on the list, which is, it is safe to take risk and initiative in your team. So you said yes, when it comes to the development, most of the client have business idea. And some of them have little knowledge of it. Or they will discuss with their colleague who are not up to date with technology. So then they ask developer to develop using those outdated technology. So the thing is that the moment as a team, we need to take risk, and we need to do our best. So that's really a good attitude. So do you take risk? Because in this team because of the quality of safety you have?

Participant 6 48:41

Yeah, so best example. When I joined for this new project, actually, the project was really all the framework party using at the moment is in version nine. But the project was in version 5.4. So first thing, we just update the project, okay, things were fine. But the coding structures were really, really, really bad. So we had a new requirement for admin panel. So from my experience, I know, admins are allowed to go everywhere, in whatever the system is. So I just make a tender, different approach. We were having something like three weeks to complete the task, and we just complete the tasks and our pm was happy. But later on, he just came to me and why did you did this in this way? I mean, the entire approach feels totally different. And we had a lot of discussions. He said, No, we shouldn't do this. We should go for the old approach. I all the time I tried to explain it, but he didn't ask it. So later, he says no You need to change this. And I have to change everything within two days. And I think for those days, I didn't have much sleep more than it was just something four hours for sleep for a day. Actually, I was working 14 hours for a day sometimes. So it was a race. Because I know that could be the best approach for admin panel. Then, a couple of weeks, we had same requirement, but there are a little bit

of difference. At this time, our lead says, If and I think we need to the same mechanism you use for the admin panel. So please use it. Then I asked, Why do you say like that, because last time you said that admin panel should have the same mechanism as in the use of panels. So why do you think I need to use a new mechanism for this one, then he said, at that time, he before joy before we guys given to the team. He was talking with us with the previous team's experience, the way they code, the way they manage the project. But after a couple of months, he know where I'm going to be honest, he always says, with with infrastructure, he always come to me. He always spoke to me and as a pawn will this be okay, but it's now when it made me concerned about the beginning, it was totally different. So at that point, I take a risk, and I was failed at that race. But now he have reconsidered to rebuild this application from A to Z with me new approach. So before three months, four months, I was faced with that race. But I think now I am passing this race because Miley want to change everything with new approach.

Researcher 52:26

So how rewarding for the quality of the admin panel was this risk? Did it help to increase the quality of the admin panel? Definitely.

Participant 6 52:38

You mean? Yes. Yeah, definitely. Because this example would be in last project. It takes it more than six seconds to fetch 1000 items. But with a new approach, we were able to do it less than in one sec less than in one second. But not 1000. But you can see everything while they scroll. That's yeah, I think six seconds and one second means in development is a big gap.

Researcher 53:19

Yeah, it's a big gap. It's almost 50% improvement. Well done. That's that's that's that's a good achievement well done. That shows your talent. I agree. Let's move to the next item and we will finish with this item. It talks about helping each other than the team. It says it is difficult for other of your team to help each other. Surprisingly, you asked you answered yes, this depends on the other member capability we can ask for help. Yes, I mean, this is positive we can ask for help from high capacity team members. So when someone needs help, it's better to go for scrum master or project manager since we time the identifies team capability. So this is positive I mean you don't like to interfere or interrupt people's work but you go to the scrum master to say this team member is better to help you Justin member is more knowledgeable to help you Yeah, this is what you mean by this answer.

Participant 6 54:29

Yeah, because if I directly call to them, Hey I need some help from you. They may be held on the next day. They are tasked maybe not completed to scrum master will ask what is the reason to prevent that? I think if the scrum master pm he knows the team where their capacities their stuff everything then he know From which guy is from which team members? Should they ask for the help? So yes, instead of directly going for the help from other team member, it's better to go for the PM.

Researcher 55:16

Okay, great. And when you help each other? What happens? Do you learn from each other? Does the quality gets better? And do you have examples?

Participant 6 55:28

So in my previous project, because at this project, I am always helping others. Because there are only two back end developers, me and my lead. In my previous project, I was working with someone, to be honest, I thought he has not much talent. But when I had calls with him, when we went through the coding, I really knew he is really talented more than me. He has the same issue is to talk to you guys. But the way he caught is totally different based on with me, because he has more speed than me. And he know those little things more than me well. So yeah. As a team, when we try to collaborate, when we ask for other helps, we can share things, as well, as we know if we have any issue with us or our coding. We say it.

Researcher 56:31

Yeah. So did you learn from this person? Did you learn from his way of coding? Yeah. So did it influence your way of coding better in a better way?

Participant 6 56:44

For a better way, actually, because the guy was actually we were coded from PHP tables coming from Java. And when he learned for the PHP, he was able to pick couple of things from Java. So it really helped me for my technical knowledge.

Researcher 57:09

So and do you help others as well? Do you contribute to other knowledge? Other? Yeah. So do you think it helps sometimes to improve the quality of their code or the quality of their work?

Participant 6 57:25

Not only that, it will help for the event process.

Researcher 57:31

for you as well. Right? So yeah, so it's a win win situation, you learn from each other, the better way to? That was really very good. I'd like to thank you a lot for the very interesting conversation and Nick Boone, we came to an end, do you have anything to add in this topic? I mean, of being safe and the work environment, feeling comfortable and confident to come forward with mistakes and things like that. If anything's we haven't talked about, you'd like to add, I'm happy to hear it.

Participant 6 58:14

Okay, it was a couple of minutes. Actually, I need to say something. So as I said,

Researcher 58:22

Yeah, go ahead.

Participant 6 58:24

Yeah. So in my previous company, I said people's new beginning, there were only three of us. And at the beginning, I didn't work for I mean, he paid a salary for me, but as a person, I didn't work for that

amount. They are our top 10 development companies in India. Each year, they select top 10 development companies. So my goal was even, it's a new company, I said all the time. Next year, we should be within this tail. So that that was my goal. So but because of someone's bad decision, because he always tried to say, you are not talented for code, you are talented for management. So because of that decision, I think they lost someone who didn't work for money, personally, because even my family always saying, stop this and have asleep. What are you doing? Please find another job. You don't need to work like this. Because they lost someone. I mean, I'm not the best and maybe not the best guy. But to be honest, I allow that joke. Allow that question. I wanted the competitor to be in first, within test within first in base comparison So, as a leader or as someone, supervisor, I personally think they should be able to identify their members. And they should be able to win their trust. If they can. The QA, the company will be more bigger and bigger, even more than meeting. So, all the time, no matter whoever the team member is, he may be not totally qualified for the requirements, but he may have something we don't see. patient, or the latest or the MSO to period should be able to say those talents.

Researcher 1:00:47

Okay. And your new team? How do you think management are differently? In your new team, because you change the companies, so how does the management now does it? How does it make you feel comfortable, motivated and using your talent in the team?

Participant 6 1:01:12

Most of the time, new management, they give opportunities for us to decide what we have to do and they listen to us. So as I said, in previous one, we, there were cost more than four hours some days. But personally, I don't like something like that in my new company, sometimes for 10 minutes cold, but I have I have one is trust. So he knows this guy will do this job. However, so I don't need to follow him all the time. When it comes for decision, a take a call. And as from last, we have something like this. Do you guys have any idea? As a team, it should come from a in a state of one person.

Researcher 1:02:01

Yeah, that's really good. Thank you very much. I enjoyed the interview. And I reached out if I need you, thank you very much. And thanks for your time. I really appreciate thank you and it was a nice discussion. Thank you for the good examples. Were really good. Thank you Participant 6. Have a good day. And good night because it's getting late.

Participant 6 1:01:22

My pleasure. I enjoyed it to. Talk soon.